

Artificial Intelligence and ELT in North Macedonia: Teachers' Beliefs and Practices

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Abstract

The dissemination of generative AI as a tool for commercial and every-day use quickly started to sow fear amongst professionals anxiously awaiting their positions to be replaced by artificial intelligence potentially making them obsolete in the workforce in general. One of the most affected professions or callings are, without a shadow of a doubt, language teachers, and especially English language teachers, as AI is initially based on English and most of the research done via internet search engines, regardless of geography, is in English.

Walking hand-in-hand with the fear of becoming obsolete is also the dread of leaving learners with a scarce and superficial knowledge of the language for straightforward communicational purposes without the depths of intertextuality and implicational information that the English language can offer. If learners are only equipped with mere communicational learning, paying attention more to language efficiency and economy than to the endless possibilities of its expressive values, the usage boils down to a lingua franca; a means to an end, and nothing more than that.

The authors of this paper propose new ways of utilising generative AI without allowing for too much independence for lower lever learners of English in order to keep them on track with a productive language learning process.

Keywords: Generative AI, English language teaching, English language learning, obsolete profession, communicational usage, deeper language learning.

1. Introduction

Over the past decade, education, and particularly language learning, has trespassed multiple paradigm shifts. These transformations have accelerated, initially with the COVID-19 pandemic, followed by the availability of ChatGPT, at the end of 2022 as an advanced language model based on generative artificial intelligence (genAI). While the pandemic mainly transferred classes and assessment in the virtual space (Clune, 2020), the rise of genAI opened and encouraged deep discussions about the efficacy and effectiveness of the current pedagogical practices and skills needed for success in the digital world. At the same time, there was a rise in justified fear about the dangers of embracing these tools unconditionally at the expense of critical thought (Bonfield et al., 2020; Ramirez-Montoya et al., 2022).

The spread of artificial intelligence as an everyday tool soon began to sow panic amongst professionals, including English language educators/teachers (ELT), as they anxiously await for their positions to become outdated. This concern is especially prominent amongst English language educators, as the large language models (LLMs) are mainly trained in English; though other world languages are not falling behind. An even bigger fear compared to being replaced by technology, is the danger of superficial learning and knowledge of the language amongst students, due to the fact that the AI LLMs put focus on economy and efficiency of communication, or mainly communication on a “need-to-know basis”, undermining and completely disregarding the richness of intertextuality and the expressive function of language. Should learning mainly boil down to a lingua franca for basic purposes, language itself turns simply into a tool or means of communication, and not a purpose in itself.

Nevertheless, the integration of technology in English language teaching is not a new phenomenon. Beginning with the use of the radio, television, mobile telephone apps, each new technological advancement wave has brought a new air of optimism, with a critical debate in hand (Salaberry, 2001). Researchers like Levy (2009) are accentuating that positive results in learning still mainly depend on pedagogy and teacher expertise, and not the tools themselves. Currently, in the era of education 4.0, AI is promoted as a revolutionary force. Empirical data already suggests that there have been positive effects in all language skills; from speech improvement and fluency (Liu & Hung, 2016; Madhavi et al., 2023), to an increase in grammatical correctness and lexical abundance, and writing as well (Dizon & Gayed, 2021; Song & Song, 2023).

While empirical research increasingly documents the effects of AI on learner performance, considerably less attention has been paid to teachers' beliefs, perceived readiness, and classroom practices, particularly in smaller educational systems. Understanding teacher cognition is critical, as pedagogical integration of AI ultimately depends not on technological affordances alone, but on teachers' perceptions, readiness and current classroom practices. This study, therefore, aims to examine the beliefs and practices of English language teachers in North Macedonia regarding generative AI, with the goal of ensuring the basis for future professional growth and development of the educational programmes.

2. Literature Review: AI in ELT

Computerised, mobilised and AI-assisted language activities are not new in the ELT field (e.g., Barreta and Maritza, 2018; Yang and Kyan, 2022). Each technological trend has brought a surge of scientific papers usually serving several purposes. Some papers' goal is to inform ELT teachers of novel tools, to highlight pedagogical and research possibilities that new technological developments have opened up, to survey ELT teachers and students about their use and preference regarding new tools, to explore how novel tools affect autonomous second language learning, and/or to test scientifically whether new tools improve learning outcomes (Garett, 1991). Discussion about how facilitative or detrimental such technological innovations are for language learning also abound in the literature. While some researchers have argued that L2 pedagogy has to take advantage of new technological tools (e.g, Dunkel, 1987), others have been more skeptical and called for a more objective and critical analysis of the correlation between increased technological sophistication and pedagogical effectiveness (Salaberry, 2001). In his review of the use of technology (radio, television, VCR, computers, mobile phones) for second language learning, Sallabery (2001) critically analyzes articles that proposed pedagogical use of technological resources published since 1916 in the *Modern Language Journal*. He cautions against the overly enthusiastic acceptance of new technologies and encourages their critical examination urging researchers and practitioners to examine the pedagogical value of such tools. He brings to light several important issues: (a) that technological advances are revolutionary but they do not always guarantee pedagogical benefits, (b) each technological wave spurs optimism, debate and a surge of research albeit with limited or flawed methodology, (c) a large number of the findings regarding the effectiveness of the use of novel learning tools are impressionistic rather than empirically

grounded, i.e., evidence for the effectiveness of a particular new tool comes from teachers and students' subjective preferences, and (d) the use of new technologies does not always serve a pedagogical purpose and hence its use is not always justifiable. This perspective is also reflected in Levy (2009) who demonstrated that meaningful learning outcomes across all language skills still primarily hinge on pedagogy, teacher expertise and learning training rather than on the learning tools themselves. In Garrett's (1991) words, 'technology should serve language learning and not vice versa'. While each technological wave has promised to revolutionise and transform language learning experience and efficiency the central debates remain the same: efficacy, learner autonomy and pedagogical alignment. It is wise to take this historical perspective into account whenever faced with a new technological boom that promises once again magic-type solutions to all educational issues pertaining to language learning.

In the current era of Industry 4.0 and Education 4.0 the prophesied revolutioniser of language learning is AI and we are witnessing the same pattern: a growing body of research attempting to document and statistically measure AI's impact on second language learning. This section, therefore, provides a brief overview of existing findings of empirical ELT-AI research. For clarity, the review will be organised around the four language skills.

2.1 AI in Speaking

Empirical studies exploring how AI technology impacts learners' speaking performance either focus on overall speaking performance, or specific sub-skills such as pronunciation or fluency. For instance, Yang and Kyun (2022) conducted a systematic review of 25 studies on AI-supported learning published from 2007 to 2021 and revealed that for the skill of speaking, pronunciation was the most common subskill being researched, followed by pedagogy and technology. This review reflects the general findings of recent empirical studies that while AI has been found to improve speaking performance, the emphasis of individual papers has varied: some found gains in fluency and pronunciation, while others in self-reported motivation and engagement.

For example, Liu and Hung (2016) used AI generated spectrograms showing a visual representation of the pitch significantly improved participants' pronunciation by reducing the flatness of pitch and intonation patterns. In another study, high-school pupils were instructed to memorise unknown vocabulary with two pronunciation teaching methods. It was revealed that the

group that received AI speech recognition teaching and practice retained the new vocabulary longer than the one which had a simple phonetic alphabet pronunciation practice (Kazu and Kuvvetli, 2023).

Madhavi et al. (2023) also investigated whether information and communication technology (ICT) and AI tools can improve students' speaking skills. An experiment with 100 participants was conducted: 50 were in an ICT group and 50 in a non-ICT group. Participants received 60 hours of training either with ICT and AI tools or with traditional methods. ICT and AI tools included films with subtitles, YouTube videos, mobile apps, and a speech-recognition software. Pre-training to post-training results demonstrated that the ICT and AI group outperformed their peers across all speaking parameters. Namely, the ICT group demonstrated higher gains in vocabulary, fluency, grammar, pronunciation and expressive ability with improvements around 70-78% compared to 50% in the non-ICT group. The authors conclude that students' communicative competence can be improved by integrating ICT and AI tools which address linguistic, social and affective barriers to speaking. Similarly, Minguan et al. (2025) explored how Liulishuo, an AI-powered mobile application, impacts undergraduate EFL students' speaking performance. A 10-week quasi-experimental study revealed that using the AI application significantly improved participants' speaking performance, in particular pronunciation and fluency. Gains in vocabulary and grammar did not reach significance.

In terms of novel pedagogical avenues, Dizon and Tand (2020) demonstrated that AI could be used as a conversational partner, or a coach in a self-directed, out-of-class autonomous second language learning. In their study learners conversed with Alexa, a personal voice assistant, for two months and self-reported that using Alexa was fun, easy to use, effective for learning and useful for lowering anxiety. Usage patterns also revealed that participants' engagement was limited suggesting a discrepancy between reported and actual usage. When participants were faced with technical and comprehension problems they had a tendency to abandon the conversation, rather than attempt repair. However, as Salaberry (2001) cautions, self-reported efficacy of new technological tools has certain limitations and does not provide reliable proof of pedagogical benefits.

2.2 AI in Writing

Early research on how AI can facilitate L2 writing focuses on AI-driven grammar checkers such as Grammarly. In general, studies have found a positive learning effect of such treatments in comparison to more traditional ones. For example, Dizon and Gayed (2021) conducted a counterbalanced study with 31 EFL students to investigate how Grammarly impacted mobile L2 writing. Participants alternated between using Grammarly (experimental condition) or not (control) for completing their writing assignments. Results demonstrated that Grammarly-assisted writing tasks in higher education had significantly fewer grammatical errors and greater lexical richness, but limited effects on fluency and syntactic complexity. The authors recommend that AI-powered writing assistant with synchronous corrective feedback and predictive text can help ease the cognitive burden L2 students often encounter and can also aid with writing with better accuracy and greater lexical variety. Building on this research, Dizon and Gayed (2024) conducted a systematic review of 24 peer-reviewed studies on Grammarly published between 2009 and 2023. One finding was that research has expanded since 2021, with a main focus on university learners in Asian educational contexts.

Similarly, Nazari et al. (2021) conducted a randomised controlled experiment investigating the effect of AI-powered writing assistant (Grammarly Premium) on 120 graduate ESL students' academic writing. The experiment consisted of two groups: an experimental one using Grammarly and a control group without AI support. Results showed that the Grammarly group not only produced more accurate texts but also reported higher levels of engagement and motivation, demonstrating that AI grammar checkers may also foster learners' self-efficacy and willingness to write in L2.

More recent studies have moved beyond grammar checkers and have explored how generative AI writing tools impact L2 writing. Unlike static grammar checkers, generative AI (GAI) serves as a "digital tutor" or co-writer, offering possibilities for brainstorming, structuring, and stylistic refinement. For instance, Fitria (2023) examined the use of ChatGPT in writing English essays, noting that it significantly aids students in organising their thoughts and generating coherent outlines, though she cautions that human oversight remains essential for factual accuracy. Similarly, Barrot (2023) discussed the 'pitfalls and potentials' of ChatGPT, highlighting that while it can democratise access to high-quality writing support, it also poses risks regarding academic

integrity and the potential loss of a student's unique authorial voice if used without critical pedagogical scaffolding. For example, Song and Song (2023) investigated the effects that ChatGPT had on university students' academic writing and motivation, and found significant gains in students' organisation, coherence, grammar, vocabulary and motivation. Fifty EFLT undergraduates were either assigned to the ChatGPT-assisted group or to the traditional instruction group. The experimental group used AI both in class and home and received real-time AI feedback on grammar vocabulary, organisation, and coherence. The control group received teacher-led instruction and feedback, but without AI tools. Results from IELTS writing tasks and a writing motivation scale revealed that the AI-assisted group significantly outperformed the control group for overall writing, organisation and coherence, language use, and motivation.

While these studies point to a beneficial impact of AI tools, both corrective and generative, on L2 writing, when used with appropriate scaffolding, they did not investigate the long-term learning and generalisation effects. A recent study sheds light on this issue. Namely, Fan et al. (2025) found that ChatGPT can significantly improve academic writing essay scores, even at times outperforming groups guided by human experts. However, no significant differences were discovered regarding knowledge gain or transfer, suggesting that while ChatGPT can improve short-term task performance, it may not foster intrinsic motivation or long-term learning outcomes.

2.3 AI in Listening

Compared to speaking and writing, fewer empirical studies have examined the impact of AI on learners' listening comprehension. For example, Alrasheedi (2024) used a quasi-experimental design with 100 university students split into an experimental group and a control group. The experimental group practiced listening comprehension using Duolingo and AI chatbot, while the control received traditional instruction. Results showed that the experimental group scored significantly higher in all listening comprehension sub-skills: literal, critical, inferential, and creative comprehension, with large effect sizes. In a different context, Xiao (2025) conducted a longitudinal randomised controlled experiment with 84 participants to investigate the impact of AI-driven speech recognition on listening comprehension, flow, and anxiety. Over an 8-week intervention the experimental group practiced with Google text-to-speech technology which

provided real-time speech-to-text transcription of the listening passages together with immediate feedback, while the control one practiced without AI. Results from the IELTS listening tests demonstrated that the experimental group achieved substantial improvements in listening scores, and reported lower anxiety and greater immersion, which was sustained during the post-testing after three weeks. These results suggest that AI can support listening comprehension by providing a scaffold during practice, but can also boost learners' affective states by reducing anxiety and foster group immersion. Finally, AI has also been found to improve listening comprehension in self-study contexts (Chaikovska et al. 2024).

2.4 AI in Reading

Research on AI in reading has mainly demonstrated a positive effect on vocabulary acquisition, reading comprehension, self-regulation, and engagement. The progress of technology has also been evident in the teaching and practicing the skill of reading. Technological advances have enabled various software applications (iStart, McNamara et al. 2006; 3D-Readers, Johnson-Glenberg 2007; Read-ToMe, Hwang et al. 2020), Intelligent Tutoring Systems (ITSs) and intelligent computer-assisted language learning (ICALL) to enter the L2 classroom. Studies have demonstrated that these softwares have a positive impact on learners' reading comprehension through provision of targeted instruction in metacognitive and cognitive strategies and extensive practice (e.g., Golan et al., 2018). While human instruction occasionally makes use of these sophisticated strategies, Elleman et al. (2022) point out that teachers' use of such strategies is often infrequent and inconsistent due to limited knowledge and insufficient classroom time. Results from a recent study (Shafiee Rad 2025) showed that longitudinal use of AI platforms for reading (Read-ToMe) led to increasing learners' reading comprehension, self-regulation, and engagement than the more traditional methods. This platform had various beneficial features that could be utilised. For instance, text-to-speech feature, built-in dictionary, compulsory comprehension questions, level adaptation, personal reading goals, immediate feedback on reading speed and accuracy, rewards, as well as personalised reading experience.

So far, research has mainly demonstrated that AI-assisted instruction positively impacts L2 vocabulary and general reading comprehension. Studies have shown that there is a significant improvement in learners L2 vocabulary when (a) AI-assisted reading with target vocabulary

density has been manipulated with AI-assisted reading (Cao and Xu 2025), (b) texts are tailored to students' proficiencies (Heilman et al. 2010), (c) vocabulary is repeatedly used through an AI game-based practice (Jackson et al. 2015), and (d) intelligent tutoring and ICALL systems were used to train learners in comprehension strategies and vocabulary gains were a by-product (McCarthy et al. 2020).

Two recent meta-analyses have also singled out vocabulary as the most frequently targeted skill in AI-assisted L2 learning. Providing additional support, studies utilising AI for L2 learning most often reported gains in vocabulary and comprehension, even though they remain limited to short-term interventions (Yang and Kyun 2020; Went and Chiu 2023).

2.5 Interim summary

Overall, empirical research on AI in ELT shows potential to facilitate language learning across language skills, although its impact varies depending on the skill, context, and pedagogical implementation. In speaking, AI-powered tools such as speech recognition systems, sound waves, and conversational agents have positively influenced learners' pronunciation, fluency, and motivation (Liu & Hung, 2016; Kazu & Kuvvetli, 2023; Madhavi et al., 2023; Mingyan et al., 2025). In writing, both corrective and generative AI applications such as Grammarly and ChatGPT, have yielded significant improvements in grammatical accuracy, lexical richness, coherences, and self-efficacy. Researchers point to the fact that learners and teachers alike, should be aware of over-reliance on AI and its detrimental effects on knowledge formation (Nazari et al., 2021; Song & Song, 2023; Fan et al., 2025). With respect to listening, there have been fewer studies, but those available point to a positive association between AI-based platforms and chatbots and learners' comprehension, anxiety, and engagement (Alrasheedi, 2024; Xiao, 2025; Chaikovska et al., 2024). Similarly, research on reading highlights that adaptive AI tutoring systems and personalised feedback consistently improve learners' vocabulary acquisition, comprehension, and self-regulation (Heilman et al., 2010; Shafiee Rad, 2025). When integrated thoughtfully and when pedagogically-justified, AI can serve as an ally of learning.

While much of the existing research documents how AI can support learners, there is still limited research on the extent to which English language teachers are familiar with the concept of AI and how they perceive and experience AI in their own geographical and pedagogical context.

In smaller educational systems such as Macedonia, understanding teachers' familiarity, beliefs and actual classroom practices is a crucial first step towards developing meaningful professional development training and support. It is therefore the purpose of this paper to survey ELT teachers and understand their beliefs and practices regarding AI in Macedonia, with the aim of documenting the current pedagogical situation, as well as providing an informed foundation for future education and curriculum development.

3. Methodology

3.1 Respondents

The respondents in this study were 37 English language teachers in Macedonia (2 males and 35 females). Email invitations containing the survey link were sent to state schools and private language schools, with a request that the questionnaire be forwarded to English language teachers. Participation was voluntary, and 37 teachers completed the survey. The majority of respondents were experienced language teachers with over 10 years of teaching experience (86.5%), followed by teachers with 5 to 8 years of teaching experience (8.1%). Only 5.4% of respondents had less than 4 years of teaching experience. A percentage of 75.5 of the respondents taught face-to-face, while only 24.3% taught both online and face-to-face. Participants also came from a diverse geographical as well as pedagogical context. Most of the participants came from the capital city Skopje, followed by Bitola, Ohrid, and Veles. In terms of where they teach, state schools were the most common (59.9%), followed by private schools (18.9%), private English language schools (10.8%), higher education (5.4%), and other (5.4%). Respondents were equally involved in teaching ages 11-13 (27%) and 14-18 (27%), followed by ages 5-10 (16.2%), and university students (5.4%). 24.3% of the respondents selected "other" and further elaborated that they usually teach a broader span of ages.

3.2 Instrument

The questionnaire used in this study was taken and adapted from the British Council report (Edmett et al., 2023). The instrument included both closed-ended and open-ended questions structured around four dimensions: (1) familiarity with AI tools, (2) beliefs about the benefits and limitations

of AI for the language skills, (3) current use of AI in their teaching and assessment, and (4) professional development needs. Closed-ended questions included five-point Likert scale items where respondents indicated their endorsement level from strongly disagree to strongly agree, as well as “click all that applies” questions. Open-ended items invited respondents to further elaborate on their views and practices.

3.3 Procedure

The questionnaire was distributed online. Participants were informed that their involvement in the study was entirely voluntary and posed no foreseeable risks. Prior to providing informed consent, respondents were also informed that they could withdraw from the study at any time without penalty.

3.4 Data Analysis

The collected data was analysed using a descriptive mixed-method approach. The quantitative items were analyzed using descriptive statistics, i.e., frequency counts and percentages. Because of the small sample size, the focus was on pattern identification rather than inferential statistics. Open-ended questions were thematically analysed by both authors.

4. Results

4.1. Familiarity with AI and tools used

Results indicated that just under half of the respondents were slightly familiar with AI (43.2%), followed by moderately familiar (32.4%), not at all familiar (13.5%), and very familiar (10.8%), suggesting a moderate familiarity overall.

In terms of AI-powered tools that respondents used, the most popular were the language learning apps (40.5%), language generation AI (40.5%), and chatbots (18.9%). Speech recognition software (16.2%), automated assessment and grading (13.5%), and text-to speech tools (8.1%) were chosen by fewer respondents. A significant percentage of respondents reported that they did not use any of the suggested AI tools. In addition to the tools listed, some respondents indicated

that they use particular classroom oriented platforms such as Tweek and MagicSchool, which use AI for lesson design and content creation, and Kahoot, Baamboozle, and Edpuzzle incorporate AI for feedback or learning analytics.

4.2. Teachers' Beliefs

The next section in the questionnaire asked respondents to rate 13 Likert-scale items statements about AI in ELT on a five-point scale from strongly disagree to strongly agree and two additional closed-ended items (See Appendix A).

Table 1

Teachers' Beliefs about AI's Impact on Improving English Skills (N = 37)

Skill	M	SD	% Agree/Strongly Agree
Speaking	3.90	0.79	64.8
Writing	4.00	0.73	70.3
Listening	4.14	0.71	78.4
Reading	4.08	0.74	75.7

Note. Percentages represent the proportion of teachers selecting each category on a five-point Likert scale (1 = strongly disagree, 5 = strongly agree).

Table 2

Teachers' Beliefs about AI's Role in English Language Teaching (N = 37)

Belief Statement	M	SD	% Agree/ Strongly Agree	% Neutral	% Disagree/ Strongly Disagree
Learners should write without AI tools.	3.6	0.9	75.6	18.9	5.4
AI can plan effective lessons.	3.9	0.8	59.5	24.3	16.2
AI is more useful for ELT than other subjects.	3.4	0.9	43.9	40.5	15.6

By 2035, AI will replace teachers.	2.6	0.8	13.5	40.5	46.0
AI makes language learning unnecessary.	2.3	0.7	10.8	16.2	73.0
Worried about AI's impact on teaching roles.	3.1	0.9	32.4	27.0	40.6
AI negatively impacts learners' ability to improve English.	2.6	0.8	21.6	45.9	32.4
Teachers have received enough AI training.	2.4	0.8	13.5	24.3	62.1

Note. Percentages represent the proportion of teachers selecting each category on a five-point Likert scale (1 = strongly disagree, 5 = strongly agree).

4.3. Teachers' needs

Table 3 shows the professional development areas the teachers expressed interest in. The most frequently selected area was *workshop on how to use AI tools* (n = 14), followed closely by *how to tailor instructional material to different levels of EL learners* (n = 12). Moderate interest was shown in *how to create exams with AI* (n = 6), while fewer teachers indicated a need for training in *how to grade using AI* (n = 3) or *how to write lesson plans with AI* (n = 1). Overall, the results suggest that teachers prioritise general familiarity with AI tools and adapting instruction to diverse learners over more specific AI-integrated teaching tasks such as grading or lesson planning.

Table 3

Professional Development Area	Count
Workshop on how to use AI tools	14
How to tailor instructional material to different levels of EL learners	12
How to create exams with AI	6
How to grade using AI	3
How to write lesson plans with AI	1

5. Discussion and Conclusion

Overall, the findings of the present study suggest that Macedonian teachers' beliefs and practices largely reflect global trends, while also revealing specific local challenges associated with integrating AI in smaller educational systems.

The reported levels of familiarity suggest that teachers' engagement with AI remains moderate rather than advanced. While most respondents indicated that they were either slightly or moderately familiar with AI tools (75.6%), only 10.8% reported being very familiar. This pattern suggests that AI has entered teachers' professional awareness; however, their familiarity may still be largely surface-level.

The most remarkable conclusion from Table 1 is the average number of teachers who believe that AI has positive effects on all four language skills, where listening and reading have scored the highest. This could suggest that Macedonian teachers are familiar with the AI tools as powerful aids in receptive skills, which correlates to the research done Alrasheedi (2024) and Xiao (2025), proving that the AI platforms seem to be lowering anxiety and improving listening immersion.

In writing ($M = 4.00$), teachers expressed considerable confidence in the usefulness of tools such as Grammarly and ChatGPT for improving linguistic accuracy, consistent with Dizon and Gayed (2021). However, a notable discrepancy emerges in Table 2: despite recognising AI's benefits for writing, 75.6% agreed that students should write without AI tools. This tension may reflect concerns about what Fan et al. (2025) term "metacognitive laziness," whereby excessive reliance on generative AI could undermine the long-term internalisation of knowledge and the development of independent proficiency.

Contrary to the concerns regarding professional obsolescence raised earlier in the paper, the findings indicate strong professional confidence among Macedonian teachers. Only 13.5% agreed that AI makes language learning unnecessary. This finding is key due to the fact that it accentuates the human component in ELT. As Salaberry (2001) argues, technological waves often generate optimism and disruption, yet pedagogical effectiveness ultimately depends on the teacher. In this study, AI is largely perceived as a productivity-enhancing tool (e.g., for lesson planning, $M = 3.9$) rather than as a substitute for the teaching process itself. Nevertheless, the fact that 32.4% of teachers reported concern about their future professional role warrants careful consideration and further investigation.

Perhaps the most critical finding concerns the perceived deficit in professional training felt by Macedonian teachers. While teachers have positive beliefs for the potential of AI, up to 62.1% stated that they have not received any or enough training. This gap highlights a challenge and stands in contrast to the expectations associated with Education 4.0.

Teachers' professional development interests further reflects this finding. The strongest demand was for practical workshops on how to use AI tools, followed by interest in personalising instructional materials for learners at different proficiency levels (Heilman et al., 2010). Notably, fewer respondents expressed interest in AI-assisted grading or lesson planning, suggesting that teachers are not seeking automation of their professional responsibilities, but rather pedagogically grounded guidance for integrating AI meaningfully into their practice.

In conclusion, data suggests that the ELT sector in Macedonia is in a state of transition. There is a high cognitive acceptance of AI (positive beliefs), but very low technical implementation due to systemic and systematic scarcity of preparatory activities in education. Instead of a "big showdown" between the teachers and AI, the results are pointing at the need for symbiosis, where AI would take over administrative and technical load, leaving room for the teacher to focus on deeper language and intercultural values that technology can and probably will not be able to replicate.

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